

The AI Register

Unthinkable Ideas, Data

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7/17/23

Dear All

Hope you are well,

Here is an edited excerpt from my statement on using AI in the classroom focusing on maintaining a *register* of the use.¹

- During the Spring 2023 Semester Artificial Intelligence (AI) arrived in my classroom as a contributor to the Assignments we were tackling. My teaching practice now includes a disclosed *AI register* for the classroom/shared learning space where I + the class members publish the AI response to our assignments and questions. Nearing the end of the Spring 2023 Semester, I (KM) concluded that Bard by Google, was the research assistant to work with via the implementation: 'Bard-rs' <https://docs.rs/crate/bard-rs/1.0.6>. Bard-rs is a beautiful rendering, built with the programming language Rust. Rust is fast, making it a good choice for high-performance applications. The tryout with Bard-rs is reported in Supplement 3 of 'Designing Assignment_1d [I]'. Bard-rs allows users to save their chat history with Bard in a Markdown file which can be source material for a *learning space AI register*² and an *internal register*.³ The *registers* will function as a record of progress. The other reasons to use Bard are no Paywall and the timeframe for searched texts appearing to run to date of usage.

¹ For the full statement in the context of the initiating assignment see *Supplement 3* of 'Designing Assignment_1d: Large Language Models and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space.' 9 Feb. 2023, <https://zenodo.org/record/7811747>. Get the latest PDF here: https://zenodo.org/record/8155031/files/ChatGPTReasoning_20230717123201_.pdf?download=1

² The learning space *AI register* is https://bit.ly/AIregister_PreventionResearch

³ I did a review of record keeping, most liking the appearance of the term *internal register* for conveying the role of record keeping and the guidance provided here: 'Record Keeping | Responsible Research.' 16 July 2023, <https://www.responsible-research.ubc.ca/evolving-topics-responsible-research/record-keeping>. I am recommending this page's: DID YOU KNOW? (1) A complete and accurate research record goes beyond clearly documenting where we obtained the research materials; why, when, and how we generate, collect or analyze data; and what our observations, interpretations, and next steps are. ...

- The Class members during the Spring 2023 Semester used a variety of AI platforms. Jarvis AI/Jasper AI was the number one choice. Jasper is marketed as a 'writer AI' returning text blocks; some members dropped these blocks into their submissions. I challenged undeclared, uncredited usage with a request for crediting. I tried to highlight the absence of speculative writing in the AI outputs. Our assignments request speculative writing, which currently appears to be beyond the reach of AI. My proposal of an *AI register* was developed during these interactions. The *AI register* will function as a collection of our conversations with AI. Some of the AI work products will likely be contributors to story discovery and the development of our analysis.
- Why a *register*: AI is in our learning space. I have proposed we make AI a go-to research collaborator by pitching its take into our conversations and crediting what we use. Good Record Keeping practices advise we record, publish AI work products on our Assignments to the under-construction https://bit.ly/AIregister_PreventionResearch.
- My proposal is for the *AI register* to be a go-to collaborator for the students and to be continuously updated with the newly revealed AI work on the problems we are tackling during the Semester. During the Spring 2023 Semester Students included AI work products in their assignment submissions; my learning space role includes aiding and guiding the use of AI.
- The *AI register* will include functioning as a record keeper for our learning space. I will also implement an *internal register* for this space/research. The reasoning behind maintaining a *AI register* and an *internal register* is to create a reviewable record of our progress to aid in any reconstruction and evaluation of the research process. I suspect not all the contents gathered with AI will be facilitating learning so the *internal register* will function to cover the decisions of editing.
- The first Assignment for the Fall 2023 *Prevention Research* course is https://bit.ly/Assignment_1_. I am publishing the Bard work product on this Assignment to the AI register, 20230711205348UTC.

A micro-debate with class members during Spring 2023 was on AI as a curator of existing info., not a creator, some members agreed, and some disagreed. The split was 50:50.

- An outcome for me was the decision to create an *AI register*; I do not know the outcomes for the student members, but I do know via my subjective sampling that members were equally distributed across used and credited usage of the AI work product, used without crediting usage, and some did not use. *I requested crediting for any usage of AI work products.*
- I checked usage by asking Bard and Skype ChatGPT (Bing's ChatGPT) if a text example was created by AI.⁴ This is a *Fool's Errand*, going-forward I will not check student work with an AI review. I will request and provide examples of crediting work and will explore the development of AI.⁵

⁴ Why Skype: Skype Conference Calls remain a good, user-friendly platform for conversing with an online student community. Skype ChatGPT is available in the same window.

⁵ The large language models (LLMs) will be constantly updated with more parameters and better text generation; detection of AI work products is likely wasting my/your time.

I(KM) try to run our learning space as an #IdeasLab; the Assignments ask for a speculative writing response and predictions on Public Health issues and futures.

- I started a Bard conversation on the creator issue. See Figure 1. Bard's response suggests that the AI future in the classroom space is a must-be-included research collaborator.

Figure 1: Crediting the work product of AI, 20230601

- I suggested to Spring 2023 members that we follow the progress of AI development by distinguishing its curating of text-based sources and asking AI to speculate on and predict

outcomes for the Public Health issues we are addressing in our learning space. My current understanding is that AI cannot predict nor speculatively write. I hope to have feedback from members in the Fall of 2023. To distinguish our work from the AI work products I will promote speculative writing on solutions to the problems we are tackling. One of the objectives for an #IdeasLab approach is *Futurism*: speculatively writing on healing the harms at the root causes of Health Disparities.⁶

Thanks for reading,

Best to you,

K Moses JD PhD

My preference for questions in and out of a Classroom setting is *Slack* ... I am @Moses.

My project work with others is described here, <https://bit.ly/EnvironmentalJusticeMatters>, a *Climate Protection Fund*TM proposal,

Coming Fall 2023:

“Prevention Research,” see <https://stjohns.digication.com/kmoses/home>,

If you share content for “Prevention Research” via Google Docs, I am at Docs.Moses@gmail.com and GoogleVoice at +13473526626.

Office Hours are Mon - Thurs 1230 to 1330 EST. And via Microsoft Teams at <https://bit.ly/OfficeHoursWithKMoses>.

⁶ On the Health Disparities: Zou et al. ‘Abstract C089: Residential Segregation Contributes to Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer Risk in African Americans in the Southeastern US’ *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, vol. 32, no. 1_Supplement, Jan. 2023, p. C089. Silverchair, <https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7755.DIS.P22-C089>. ‘Background: It remains unclear why African Americans (AA) have [a] higher incidence of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and develop the disease 5 years earlier than Non-Hispanic Whites (NHW). [’